

Corticospinal and corticoreticulospinal projections have discrete but complementary roles in chronic motor behaviors after stroke

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	Behavior			TMS		
	Stroke	Healthy	Group effect	Stroke	Healthy	Group effect
Excitement	10 (6–10)	8 (5–10)	$z = 1.9, p = 0.057$	10 (7–10)	8 (3–10)	$z = 3.6, p = 0.0003$
Alertness	8 (1–10)	7 (1–10)	$z = 1.7, p = 0.241$	7.5(3–10)	6 (1–10)	$z = 1.9, p = 0.057$
Discomfort	5 (0–12)	2 (0–12)	$z = 0.4, p = 0.719$	5.5 (0–9)	6 (1–9)	$z = -0.1, p = 0.901$
Hours of sleep	6 (3–9)	7 (4–8)	$z = -1.2, p = 0.235$	6 (3–9)	7 (4–8)	$z = -0.5, p = 0.614$
Number of alcoholic drinks	0 (0–0)	0 (0–2)	$z = -1.7, p = 0.095$	0 (0–1)	0 (0–2)	$z = -1.2, p = 0.230$
Number of caffeinated drinks	1 (0–2.5)	1 (0–3)	$z = -0.6, p = 0.582$	1 (0–6.5)	1 (0–4)	$z = -0.04, p = 0.966$

Supplemental Table 1. Psychometric measurements. Psychometric measurements at the behavior and TMS testing visits. Median (range) shown. Excitement, alertness, and discomfort were scored from 0–10, with 10 being highest. Hours of sleep and number of alcoholic and caffeinated drinks were counted from the 24 hours preceding the visit. Stroke subjects were more excited to participate at the TMS visit ($p = 0.0003$). Significant *group* effects are bolded.